

Query Term Recommendation Using Domain-Specific Ontologies and Sentence Transformers

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Abstract

Purpose

This study focuses on enhancing the search capabilities of the Terminology Service (TS) within NFDI4ENERGY domain. Keyword-based search engines like SOLR often face challenges in retrieving semantically relevant query recommendations, especially in handling synonyms, abbreviations, misspellings, and conceptual queries. To complement SOLR, we developed a Recommendation Service that aims to enhance the accuracy and relevance of search results through semantic understanding. The effectiveness of this work will be evaluated through a user survey.

Methodology

We employed the Sentence-BERT model to develop a semantic Query Recommendation Service tailored to the Terminology Service (TS). This involved embedding text corpora from four research domains including NFDI4ENERGY and deploying a REST API to enable semantic query-based retrieval of ontology entities. The service operates alongside SOLR, with each addressing different aspects of search requirements.

The effectiveness of the Recommendation Service will be evaluated through a user survey. In the survey, participants will be presented with specific user queries and the corresponding search results recommended by the service. Survey respondents will rank these results based on their relevance and usefulness, providing valuable feedback to assess the service's performance.

Findings

The integration of the Recommendation Service with SOLR significantly improves search outcomes. While SOLR excels in fast, keyword-based retrieval, the Recommendation Service

enhances results by understanding the semantic meaning of queries. It effectively handles synonyms, abbreviations, misspellings, and conceptual queries, providing enriched results referred to as *Concept Matches*. This complementary approach has the potential to enhance user experience in ontology-based searches.

Value

By integrating the strengths of SOLR and the Recommendation Service, this solution addresses the limitations of keyword-based search while preserving its advantages. We aim to evaluate whether the combined approach offers contextually relevant results and improves the efficiency of searches within Terminology Service through future user surveys.